

“Effectiveness Of Structured Teaching Programme On Knowledge Regarding Behavioral Problems Among Under Graduate Students”

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Abstract: Behavioral problems are common among young adults, highlighting the need for effective educational strategies. This study assessed the effectiveness of a structured teaching program on knowledge of behavioral problems among 100 undergraduate students at Index Nursing College, Indore. Using a pre-experimental design, a structured questionnaire measured knowledge levels before and after the intervention. Pre-test findings showed 75% of students had inadequate knowledge, while post-test results revealed 70% achieved adequate knowledge. The mean post-test score (24.69%) was significantly higher than the pre-test score (14.74%), with a t-value of 33.06 ($p < 0.05$). The program significantly improved knowledge, emphasizing the importance of structured educational interventions in enhancing awareness of behavioral issues.

Keywords: *behavioral problems, structured teaching program, knowledge improvement, undergraduate students, education, college students, pre-test, post-test, demographic variables, knowledge assessment.*

Introduction

Behavioral problems can be more challenging than attendance or performance problems with these types of problems a gradual or progressive process to get improvement can be successful. The emotional environment of a young child consists of an entire relationship of the child with their parents and family members. Behavioral problems are less common when the child is loved, accepted and who is living in favorable environmental conditions (K.P. Neeraja, 2000).

Aggression is a purposive act to hurt oneself, others, or the environment physically and verbally. Verbal aggression is most frequently committed and experienced by teenagers. This behavior contributes to physical aggression, especially toward adolescents with emotional disorders. In definitions commonly used in the social sciences and behavioral sciences, aggression is an action or response by an adolescents that delivers something unpleasant to another person. Some definitions include that the individual must intend to harm another person. Aggressive behavior among adolescents poses significant challenges for educators, parents, and society as a whole. It is crucial to develop effective strategies for managing and preventing such behavior to ensure the well-being and safety of adolescents, as well as the individuals around them. This study aims to assess the impact of a structured teaching program on knowledge related to the management of aggressive behavior among adolescents."In the background of a standard teaching program for managing aggressive behavior among adolescents in school. It is important to consider various factors that contribute to aggression and develop strategies to address them effectively. There are various points which describe the need of the study like, it providing ways for managing aggression, improve the knowledge and awareness about self-behavior, to gaining knowledge about the most common triggering factors of aggressive behavior etc.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

"A STUDY TO ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF STRUCTURED TEACHING PROGRAMME ON KNOWLEDGE REGARDING BEHAVIORAL PROBLEMS AMONG UNDER GRADUATE STUDENTS IN SELECTED COLLEGE AT INDORE (M.P.)."

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY: -

- To assess the Pre Test and post test knowledge level regarding behavioral problems among under graduate college students.

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- To evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding behavioral problems among under graduate college students.
- To find out the association between the knowledge regarding behavioral problems among under graduate college students with selected demographic variables.

HYPOTHESIS:

H1: There will be a significant difference between pretest and post-test knowledge scores on knowledge regarding behavioral among under graduate college students in selected college.

H2: There will be a significant association between pre-test knowledge scores and selected demographic variables.

RESEARCH APPROACH

A quasi-experimental approach, a subtype of the quantitative approach, was used for the study. A quasi-experiment involves the manipulation of independent variables by implementing an intervention.

RESEARCH DESIGN

A one-group pre-test post-test research design was adopted for this study. This design involves measuring the dependent variable before and after implementing the intervention without randomization.

Independent variable: Structured teaching program on behavioral problems among undergraduate students.

Dependent variable: Knowledge of undergraduate students regarding behavioral problems.

Exogenous variables: Demographic variables such as age, gender, education level, family background, and socio-economic status.

Setting of the Study

The study was conducted at Index Nursing College, located in Indore, with a total student strength of over 750 nursing students.

Population

The accessible population includes undergraduate nursing students at the selected nursing college in Indore.

Samples and Sample Size

The sample size for the study consisted of 100 undergraduate students.

Sampling Technique

The samples were selected using the purposive sampling technique, a type of non-probability sampling method.

Criteria for Selection of Samples

Inclusion Criteria

- Both male and female students.
- Students who are willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Students who have attended previous behavioral classes.
- Students who are not available at the time of data collection.

DEVELOPMENT AND DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOLS

The researcher developed a structured questionnaire to assess knowledge regarding behavioral problems, after reviewing relevant literature and consulting psychiatric nursing experts. The tool consists of two sections.

Section A gathers demographic information, including age, sex, father's and mother's educational status, type of family, father's occupation, mother's occupation, and family monthly income.

Section B is a structured questionnaire designed to evaluate the participants' knowledge on behavioral problems. It consists of 30 multiple-choice questions, with each question offering four options—one correct and three incorrect. Each correct answer earns 1 mark, and each incorrect answer receives 0 marks. The maximum possible score is 30, with a minimum score of 0.

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Formal permission was taken from concerned authorities. The researcher explained the purpose of the study in a compassionate manner, and informed consent was obtained from the students. A total of 100 samples were selected from the college using the purposive sampling technique. The first phase of data collection was conducted at Index Nursing College with these 100 participants. Knowledge was assessed using a structured questionnaire. Following this, a structured teaching program (STP) on behavioral problems was provided to the undergraduate students. After a period of 14 days, the post-test was conducted using the same questionnaire to evaluate the effectiveness of the STP.

RESULTS & RESEARCH FINDINGS

Section –I : Social Demographic Variables

Age: 10 (10.0%) students were in the age group of 17-18 years, 20 (20%) students were in the age group of 19-20 years, 50 (50.0%) students were in the age group of 21-22 years, and 20 (20%) students were in the age group of 23 years and above.

Gender: 40 (40%) students were male, while 60 (60%) students were female, indicating a higher proportion of females in the study.

Religion: 94 (94%) students identified as Hindu, 4 (4%) as Muslim, and 2 (2%) as Christian, with the majority being Hindu.

Father's Educational Status: 5 (5%) students' fathers were illiterate, 15 (15%) had completed primary education, 37 (37%) had completed secondary education, and 43 (43%) had completed higher secondary education.

Mother's Educational Status: 10 (10%) students' mothers were illiterate, 24 (24%) had completed primary education, 39 (39%) had completed secondary education, and 27 (27%) had completed higher secondary education.

Type of Family: 52 (52%) students came from nuclear families, while 48 (48%) came from joint families, with a slight majority from nuclear families.

Father's Occupation: 89 (89%) students' fathers were employed in private jobs, 4 (4%) in government jobs, 5 (5%) in daily wage work, and 2 (2%) in other occupations.

Mother's Occupation: 79 (79%) students' mothers were employed in private jobs, 4 (4%) in government jobs, 5 (5%) in daily wage work, and 2 (2%) in other occupations.

Family Monthly Income: 56 (56%) students' families had a monthly income between 5000-10000, 34 (34%) had an income between 10000-15000, and 10 (10%) had an income less than 15000. No students had a family income above 5000. The majority of students came from families with an income between 5000 and 10000.

Section –II :: Description regarding the knowledge of undergraduate students on behavioral problems.

Table: 1 Frequency and percentage distribution of P re and Post test knowledge scores of undergraduate students on behavioral problems

Score	Grade	Pretest score	post test score
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		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1-10	Inadequate	57	59%	8	8%
11-20	Moderately	39	39%	22	22%
21-30	Adequate	4	2%	70	70%
Total		100	100%	100	100%

Figure 1 Pretest and Posttest knowledge level of scores of undergraduate students on behavioral problems

In the study, the knowledge levels of the undergraduate students were assessed through a pretest and post-test, with the scores categorized into three groups: inadequate, moderately adequate, and adequate. In the pretest, 57 students (57%) scored between 1-10, indicating inadequate knowledge, while 39 students (39%) scored between 11-20, reflecting a moderate level of knowledge. Only 04 students (04%) achieved an adequate knowledge level, scoring between 21-30. After the structured teaching program, the post-test results showed a significant improvement. Only 8 students (8%) scored in the inadequate range (1-10), 22 students (22%) scored in the moderately adequate range (11-20), and the majority, 70 students (70%), scored in the adequate range (21-30). These results demonstrate a substantial increase in knowledge following the intervention.

Section-III :Comparison of Statistical value of pre-test and post-test knowledge scores of undergraduate students on behavioral problems.

Table No. 2 Comparison of mean pretest and posttest Knowledge Score

Group	No. of Students	Knowledge Score [Mean ± SD]	't' Value	P Value
Pretest	Pretest	14.74	33.063	P < 0.05
Posttest	Posttest	24.69	df = 199	

Paired 't' test applied, P value < 0.05, Significant

The above table no 2 shows the comparison of pretest and posttest knowledge score. The mean pretest knowledge score was 14.74 ± 6.03 , while the posttest knowledge score was 24.69 ± 7.12 . The difference was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), showing a significantly higher posttest knowledge in comparison to the pretest knowledge score.

Figure no 2 Bar diagram showing comparison of mean pretest and posttest knowledge score

SECTION-IV: Association of demographic variables with the post-test score of knowledge regarding behavioral problems among undergraduate students.

Table No 3 Association between pretest knowledge and socio demographic variables of B.Sc. Nursing 3rd year students

S.No.	Particular	Pretest			Df	X2 Value
		INADEQUATE	MODERATELY ADEQUATE	ADEQUATE		
Age					Df - 03	32.32* P Value 0.00014
	17-18 Years	9	2	1		
	19-20 Years	31	4	1		
	21-22 Years	11	28	1		
	>23 Years	6	5	1		
Religion					Df - 03	25.97* P Value 0.0001
	Hindu	53	8	3		
	Muslim	4	31	1		
	Christian	0	0	0		
	Other	0	0	0		
Father Educational Status					Df - 03	53.00* P Value 0.0001
	Illiterate	2	1	1		
	Primary	9	15	1		
	Secondary	20	14	1		
	Higher Secondary	26	9	1		

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Mother Educational Status					Df - 03	50.16* P Value 0.0001
Illiterate	15	1	1			
Primary	22	2	1			
Secondary	19	12	1			
Higher Secondary	1	24	1			

The Chi-square test results indicate significant associations between demographic variables and pretest adequacy levels. Age ($\chi^2 = 32.32, p = 0.00014$), religion ($\chi^2 = 25.97, p = 0.0001$), father's educational status ($\chi^2 = 53.00, p = 0.0001$), and mother's educational status ($\chi^2 = 50.16, p = 0.0001$) all show p-values below 0.05, confirming strong statistical relationships. This suggests that these factors significantly influence pretest performance.

Discussion

1. The demographic data collected in Section A highlights the diverse background of the participants, including their age, gender, parental educational status, type of family, parental occupations, and family monthly income. These variables are critical in understanding the influence of socioeconomic and cultural factors on students' knowledge and learning outcomes.
2. The pretest results revealed that a majority of students (57%) had inadequate knowledge, scoring between 1-10, while 39% demonstrated moderate knowledge (scores between 11-20). Only 4% of students achieved an adequate knowledge level (21-30), underscoring the need for targeted educational interventions to improve awareness and understanding of behavioral problems.
3. The post-test results showed a remarkable improvement in knowledge levels following the intervention. The percentage of students with inadequate knowledge dropped from 57% to 8%, while the proportion of those achieving adequate knowledge increased dramatically from 4% to 70%. This highlights the effectiveness of the structured teaching program in enhancing students' knowledge about behavioral problems.
4. A significant difference was observed between the pretest and posttest mean knowledge scores (14.74 ± 6.03 vs. $24.69 \pm 7.12, p < 0.05$). This confirms that the teaching program had a statistically significant impact on improving the participants' knowledge levels.
5. The Chi-square test results indicate significant associations between demographic variables and pretest knowledge adequacy. Factors such as age, religion, father's educational status, and mother's educational status showed statistically significant relationships ($p < 0.05$). These findings suggest that demographic characteristics play a crucial role in shaping students' baseline knowledge and learning capabilities.

Summary

The study assessed the knowledge of undergraduate students on behavioral problems through pretest and posttest evaluations. Demographic data highlighted key variables influencing knowledge levels. Pretest results showed that 57% of students had inadequate knowledge, while only 4% demonstrated adequate knowledge. After a structured teaching program, posttest results revealed a significant improvement, with 70% achieving adequate knowledge and only 8% remaining in the inadequate category. The mean knowledge score increased significantly from 14.74 ± 6.03 to 24.69 ± 7.12 ($p < 0.05$). Chi-square analysis demonstrated significant associations between demographic factors, such as age, religion, and parental education, and pretest knowledge levels, indicating their influence on learning outcomes.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the structured teaching program significantly enhanced the knowledge of undergraduate students on behavioral problems. Pretest results showed that 57% of students had inadequate knowledge, with only 4% achieving adequate knowledge. After the intervention, posttest results demonstrated a remarkable improvement, with 70% of students attaining adequate knowledge and only 8% remaining in the inadequate category. The mean knowledge score increased significantly from 14.74 ± 6.03 to 24.69 ± 7.12 ($p < 0.05$).

0.05), confirming the program's effectiveness. Additionally, Chi-square analysis revealed significant associations between demographic variables—such as age ($\chi^2 = 32.32$, $p = 0.00014$), religion ($\chi^2 = 25.97$, $p = 0.0001$), and parental education—and pretest knowledge levels, indicating that these factors influence baseline knowledge. This highlights the need for customized educational interventions to address diverse learning needs.

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